

INTERFACIAL ENGINEERING IN ORGANIC/INORGANIC NANOCOMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

The influence of interface coherence between organic polymer matrix and metal/metal oxide reinforcement is investigated, based on the anchoring density at the interface. Methods of increasing anchoring density, as well as the resulting enhanced mechanical properties are also proposed.

Keywords: Hybrid composites, Metal oxide, metal nanocomposites, interfacial engineering

ORGANIC/INORGANIC INTERFACE IN COMPOSITES

In order to improve mechanical properties of polymers, inclusions (fibers, whiskers, platelets, or particles) are included in the matrix as reinforcements to form a composite. Improvements in properties can often be found even at relatively low filler content in traditional composites reinforced with micron-sized inclusions. Recently, more sophisticated techniques were developed to make “nanocomposites” by using nano-sized inclusions, with least one dimension in the range from 1-100 nm. Unlike traditional composites, the effect of nano-sized (vs. micron-sized) particles on the mechanical properties of polymer matrix composites and the mechanisms and factors contributing to the material response is still an open question.

Correlating material properties with filler size has become a topic of great interest, both theoretically and experimentally since current micromechanics approach which are very effective in predicting effective properties of composites with micron size particles are not so effective with nanoparticles, although these theories are independent of particle size. Predictions based on classical composites theory shows improved mechanical properties with better interfacial bonding between polymer matrix and particles, although experimental results show mixed results. The nature of interfacial bonding is also an ambiguous factor. Most of the existing composites theory utilize the differing properties of the constituents, volume fractions of the components, and the distribution of the particles in order to calculate the composite modulus. Experimental show a somewhat different picture: different nano-composite systems show different patterns, in some cases inclusions improves mechanical properties while in others properties are diminished. The specific reasons for this behaviour is not fully understood, but several theories have been introduced to explain some of the changes in material morphology and behaviour that are observed at the nano-scale. One of main parameter that affects the behaviour of composites reinforced with nanoparticles is the structure of the

interface between particles and the matrix. Mechanical properties can be correlated with the structure of the interface, for composites with nanoparticle inclusions (Figure 1). The molecular conformation, and thus the properties of the interphase layer is different than the bulk and this layer extends beyond the adsorption layer of the polymer matrix chains adsorbed to the particle surface. Our experiments shows that the structure and properties of the interphase play an important role in understanding the properties of a composite. Due to the large surface area, interphase layer is one of the most important factors that determine the composite properties.

The polymer nanocomposite systems we studied include poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) and polystyrene (PS) composites containing alumina (Al_2O_3) and magnetite (Fe_3O_4) nanoparticles. The structure and density of the interface of these systems are characterized using the results from thermal gravimetric analysis (TGA) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FT-IR) is used to calculate the nature of bonding between polymer and nanoparticle surfaces and the density of the interface for two PMMA-based nanocomposite systems. Although Al_2O_3 nanoparticles are more reactive with the polymer matrix than Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles, the interface interaction strength is not as strong as in the neat matrix, leading to an interface with lower density. Tensile testing, dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA), and nanoindentation tests are used to characterize mechanical properties. A new method for characterizing the degree of nanoparticle flocculation in a composite is also provided, which will be useful in evaluating nanoparticle clustering.

One of the key factors that characterize the interphase region is the number of anchoring points polymer matrix chains make with particles. From the TGA and FTIR results, the number of anchoring points per unit area are calculated, and how the number of anchoring points influence the mechanical properties of the composite, especially the modulus, was investigated. The density of anchoring points show a non-linear dependence on modulus, but the pattern shows that higher anchoring density is required for higher modulus. Thus, the anchoring density has a strong direct influence as much as the volume fraction of the metal particles. The effect of curvature of the particle on the mechanical properties of the composite was also characterized.

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Figure 1: Interphase morphology in particle reinforced composites